

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF GHARANI W.S.R TO IBS**¹Dr. Chinmayee Sahu, ²Dr. Pragya Priyadarshini Mallik, ³Dr. Santilata Sahoo**¹P.G Scholar, P.G Deptt. of Kayachikitsa, G.A.M, Puri.²Professor & HOD, P.G Deptt. of Kayachikitsa, G.A.M, Puri.³Associate Professor, P.G Deptt. of Kayachikitsa, G.A.M, Puri.Article Received on
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Kayachikitsa, G.A.M, Puri.**ABSTRACT**

Grahani springs from Dhatu "graha" which suggests "to catch" "to hold" or "to get". The word Grahani in ayurveda is related to Agni (digestive fire) which helps in the metabolism and digestion of food. Ayurvedic texts describe the ingestion, digestion, absorption and assimilation of Aahaar by Grahani. Normally it retains the undigested food and releases the digested stuff through the side of its lumen. Any disturbance in Agni leads to an improper digestion of food. Grahani roga is correlated with IBS (Irritable Intestinal Syndrome) which is characterised by a group of symptoms that can significantly undermine the quality of life of the patient. It is a functional gastrointestinal disorder characterized by a group of symptoms

accompanied together that include abdominal pain and changes in the consistency of bowel movement. Etiological factor include genetics, life time events, environment and changes in motility, visceral sensitivity, epithelial permeability, gastrointestinal flora. Prevalence of IBS in world has been estimated to be 11.2% and in India is 4.2%-7.7%. It is 3 times more common in women and people of working age.

KEYWORD- Grahani, Agni, Mala pariksha, IBS.**INTRODUCTION**

Ayurveda has its unique concept of Trayopastambha^[1] which are Ahara, Nidra and Brahmacharya which is an aid for the balance of Tridosha's. According to Ayurveda, the growth, nourishment, procreation, and dissolution of living beings are all the result of food consumed.^[2] Ayurveda emphasises the importance of Ahara by a reference which says that all the things that help to lead a quality life such as strength, intellect, complexion, cheerfulness,

good voice, happiness, contentment, intellect etc are dependent on Ahara.^[3] Acharya Kashyapa even considered Ahara as Mahabhaishajya as it is the one thing that promotes health in both diseased and normal people.^[4] If this Ahara is not proper in terms of quantity or quality, it will eventually lead to the manifestation of various diseases. Grahani is the structural seat of Agni which retains the food until it is fully digested and then passes it into the Pakwashaya.^[5] The Tridoshaja disorder of digestive system which is due to the vitiation of Pachaka pitta, Samana Vayu and Kledaka Kapha, in which there will be impairment of Agni, which eventually vitiates the structure Grahani is called as Grahani roga.^[6] Irritable Bowel Syndrome (IBS) is a functional disorder that is common in almost all parts of the world. The exact cause of IBS is not understood till now, but several factors such as stress, diet and hormonal changes may sometimes trigger or worsen the symptoms. The symptoms commonly encountered include abdominal pain or discomfort, bloating, diarrhoea, constipation etc. The prevalence of IBS all over the world is estimated to be 11.2% whereas in India, it is estimated to be between 4.2% to 7.7%.^[7] The symptomatologies of IBS mimics the symptoms explained in Grahani. The treatment explained in Ayurvedic classics effectively manages the symptoms mentioned above.

ETIOLOGICAL FACTORS^[8]

- Abhojanat, Ajeernabhojanat, Attibhojanaat, Visamasanat, Asatmya Guru, Ruksa and Sandusta Bhojanat
- Vyadhikarshanat and Vegavidharana
- Stress, anxiety and grief
- In disciplinary life style and bad food habits
- Unhygienic environmental condition
- Nutritional insufficiency
- Contagious predominance
- Improper functioning of digestive fire
- Diseased condition which weakened Agni
- Virudha-Ahara
- Avoidance of concept of Desha and Kala during consumption of food stuffs
- Excessive use of antibiotics.

SYMPTOMS^[9,10,11]

According to Acharaya the predominant symptoms of disease are; Aalasya, Trishna, Aanvidaah, Chir Pakka, Balakshaya and Gaurvam, etc.

Other symptoms of diseases are Aruchi, Kasa, Karnakshveda and Antrakunjana.

Intestinal spasms, diarrhea, constipation and abdominal pain also observed in acute condition.

FUNCTIONS OF GRAHANI^[12]

Grahani is seat of Agni and it is so called since it holds/retains the food (for proper digestion and assimilation). Grahani, supported by Agni, holds undigested food and pushes forward digested food. Agni weakens due to Vidagdha Ahara, Murchita Dosha, afflicted by improperly digested food. (Dosha associated with Ama) it vitiates the Grahani and releases food in the form of Ama i.e., undigested form extremely enraged Vatadi Dosha separately or together corrupts the Grahani. Then the Grahani leaves the food that has been eaten or left undisturbed again and again. Grahani disease is a chronic diarrhea characterized by pain, bad odour, loose motions, or thin (bile) discharge.

NIDANA OF GRAHANI ROGA

Agni vitiation can be caused by excessive starvation, humouring in food intake, and upset stomach, Overeating, irregular feeding habits, distasteful food, excessively nutritionally high-quality food, cold or dry foods, thinness, contamination, and improper procedures are common health issues, like Vamana, Virechana and Sneha, thinness of body due to disease, sudden migration to unsuitable place and of time and of season, suppression of natural urges are causes for vitiation of Agni. Thus, vitiated Agni is unable to digest even the light food. This vitiated digestive agent forms an intermediate substance called Ama, which turns sour (Shukta) during fermentation and finally turns in poisonous substance (Amavisha).^[13]

Annavisha, when associated with Pitta, causes Daha, morbid thirst, oral diseases, Amlapitta, acid peptic disorders, and other pitta-related conditions, while when associated with kapha, it leads to Yakshma, Peenas, and Prameha (20 types of diabetes) and various other Kaphaja disorders, whereas several Vatika disease are caused by association of Vata with the Annavisha. The Annavisha when enters renal system, urine related disorders occur; similarly, Kukshigata Roga (ailments related to abdomen) have their origin when Sakrita (faeces) is

involved. Rasadi Pradoshaja Vikara (tissue related ailments) occur when Rasadi Srotas are involved.^[14]

IMPORTANCE OF AGNI IN GRAHANI ROGA

- The Vishamagni (improper Agni) causes irregularity in digestion and therefore defective formation of Dhatu takes places.
- Tikshanagni (excessive Agni) when associated with little quantity of fuel (in the form of food) causes depletion of Dhatu (tissue elements).
- Samagni, If Agni is Sama., in balanced condition and correct diet regimen (as explained in Ca.Su.5 and Ca.Vi.1/21) are also followed then there is proper digestion of food which helps in maintaining proper balance within the Dhatu.
- Durbala (weak) Agni brings about partial digestion of food. These partially digested bio substances then enter in circulation, which may move either in upward or downward direction.^[15]

MODERN ASPECT OF GRAHANI ROGA (IBS)

IBS, also known as spastic colitic, is an intestinal condition causing stomach pain, diarrhoea, constipation, bloating, and gas, with individual differences making diagnosis difficult. Irritated bowel syndrome (IBS) is a functional gastrointestinal condition characterized by abdominal pain, irregular movements, and disorganized defecation, often without visible anatomical abnormalities.^[16]

IBS is a disease linked to various extra-intestinal disorders, sexual dysfunctions, urinary complaints, and psychiatric disorders. Ayurveda explains it as a result of altered Agni & Dosa Dusti, affecting Agni's functional dependence, Dhatus, and worried Srotas.

Rasavahasrotas, as well as Ahara Viharas, which result in Vatakopa. Intestinal sensitivity, motility, secretion, and permeability are all significantly affected by psychological stress, and the underlying process is closely related to mucosal immune activation, changes in the central nervous system, peripheral neurons, and gastrointestinal microbiota.

September 2022 after some time, any Sharirika Roga that a person has may transform into Manasik Roga, and the same Samprapti (pathogenesis) applies to the transformation of Manasik Roga into Sharirika Roga. This demonstrates that Ayurveda has made the most of the significance of Manas in the development of diseases.

The gut-brain axis and the microbiota-gut-brain axis are affected by stress-induced changes in neuro endocrine-immune pathways, which in turn cause symptom flare-ups or exacerbation in IBS. Since IBS is a stress-sensitive disorder, managing stress and the reactions that stress causes should be the main focus of treatment.^[17]

The Rome 3 criteria are used to rate IBS. Recurrent abdominal pain or discomfort lasting at least three days or a month and being linked to two or more of the following are the requirements.^[18]

- An alteration in defecation.
- The onset of a change in bowel frequency.
- The onset of the change in stool composition.

AYURVEDA MANAGEMENT OF GRAHANI ROGA

The traditional text of Ayurveda suggested that Grahani Roga may be treated by following concept of Langhana and using Deepana and Pachana medicines which help to potentiate Agni and eliminate ama. Purgation therapy with stimulant drugs also helps to remove Ama. Butter milk (Takra) also suggested by ancient Acharya for treatment of Grahani.^[19,20]

Specific ayurveda treatment for Grahani roga

Vataja Grahani^[21]

1. Niruhavasti, Virechana and Anuvasanvasti
2. Nagaradi kwatha
3. Abhayadi kashaya
4. Panhchmuladya Taila

Pittaja Grahani^[22]

1. Virechana
2. Chandanadya ghritam
3. Tikataghrita

Kaphaja Grahani^[23]

1. Vamana
2. Pippalyadya choorna
3. Madhukasava, Duralabhasava,
4. Haridradya kshara, Duralabhadya kshara

Life style modification in Grahani Roga

Modification in life style and balanced diet regime along with consideration of Pathya Apathya help to cure Grahani.

Diet modification

- Modification in diet pattern towards healthy eating habits boosts Agni & prevents chances of Grahani.
- Meal should be consumed at regular intervals.
- Junk foods, allergic foods and food difficult to digest should be avoided.
- Ayurveda mentioned balanced diet under Sansarjana Krama with routine diet plan depending on the Prakriti of the individual. Thus, patient of Grahani recommended to follow diet pattern of Sansarjana Krama.
- One should avoid Abhojanat, Ajeernabhojanat, Attibhojanaat, Visamasanat, Asatmya and Sandusta Bhojanat
- Preparation and consumption of unhygienic food articles. Diet containing balanced nutritional value need to be adopted.
- Virudha-Ahara must be avoided; means one should consume diet as per his/her internal constitution by following concept of Desha and Kala.

Behaviour modification

Grahani symptoms can be triggered by behavioural factors like fear, grief, stress, and sleeplessness, suggesting the need to manage these to prevent depression affecting Agni.

Maintaining normal metabolic functioning requires positivity and enthusiasm, while avoiding excessive thinking and chintan habits can affect digestion, as brain circulation is primarily associated with the intestine.

One should consume diet by following rules of Swasthwarita in proper manner so to achieve max. beneficial effect of consumed food.

Daily regimen modification/Exercise and Yoga

Regular exercise is essential for strengthening the body and Agni, and should be done at specific times throughout the day.

Mediation, Yoga, and Pranayama can help reduce stress and increase stress resistance, while Ayurveda recommends daily regimens like Ritucharya and Dinacharya for beneficial results.

Dhyan and Shodhna procedure, after fixed interval, also provides beneficial effects in Grahani.^[19]

Importance of Butter Milk^[24]

For a patient suffering from the Grahani Dosha, butter milk is the excellent drink because it stimulates the power of digestion, it is Grahi and easily digestible. Butter milk is sweet, sour, astringent in taste; light and dry in properties, hot in potency and sweet in metabolism.

Because of Madhura (sweet) Vipaka, it does not cause aggravation of Pitta. Because of its astringent taste, hot in potency, it is useful for counteracting the aggravated Kapha. Because of the sweet and sour taste, it is useful for counteracting the aggravated Vayu. When freshly prepared it does not cause burning sensation.

CONCLUSION

Grahani is a digestive fire disease affecting Annavaha Srotas and life style patterns, causing abdominal pain, bloating, and disturbed bowel habits. Ayurveda offers various formulations and therapeutic modalities for management.

Tridoshatmaka disease of digestive fire occurs due to the vitiation of Agni; Jatharagni, Saman Vayu, Pachak Pitta and Kledaka Kapha. Disease characterized by abdominal pain, bloating and disturbed bowel habits.

Ayurveda offers wide range of formulations and therapeutic modalities along with suggestions to modify life style pattern which overall offers beneficial effects in the management of Grahani Roga.

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